

Supplementary Material

A. Revising crucial technologies – adding new parameters

Since heat pumps will play a significant role in (de-)centralized heat supply in the future, their modeling is revised for GENeSYS-MOD. Heat pumps use ambient heat and raise it to a higher temperature level, usually with electricity. By utilizing ambient heat, heat pumps can achieve higher efficiencies than Power-to-Heat (Pth/P2H) systems that only convert electricity into heat directly. The efficiency of heat pumps depends on the temperature level of the respective ambient temperature and the required temperature at the heat pump outlet (i.e., the temperature of the supply of the heating circuit in the house or the district heating network).

Since, in most cases, source temperature levels vary throughout the year, the efficiency needs to be adjustable within a year. However, in GENeSYS-MOD, the efficiency is only variable with respect to the modeling year but is invariant throughout the year and constant at each modeled hour.

So far, the time dependency of heat pumps is determined like for fluctuating renewables such as wind and photovoltaics (PV). In the case of wind and solar, the hour-dependent *Capacity Factor* is used to adjust the available capacity of the technologies. For PV, the capacity factor at night is zero, i.e., when the sun is not shining, 0% of the installed capacity of PV is available for power production.

There is a more suitable way for heat pumps to implement variability than adjusting the capacity factor. In contrast to PV and wind, the heat pump has two input variables: the used ambient heat and electricity. If the input temperature decreases, the power supply needs to increase to provide the same heat output. The fluctuation of the ambient heat source can be compensated in the heat pump by increased electricity consumption. This substitution allows the available capacity to remain the same, and only the ratio of electricity to heat input changes. This is enabled by the introduction of a time-dependent efficiency parameter. If the capacity factor remains unchanged, the model will not build additional capacity, as could be the case if the adjustment is made using the capacity factor.

The calculation of the time-varying efficiency parameter is derived from the efficiency equation of heat pumps. For heat pumps, the efficiency is often referred to as the coefficient of performance (COP).

The heat pump coefficient of performance is determined by $COP = \frac{Q_c}{W}$, with Q_c being the heat output and W the electricity input.

The COP depends on the level of the input temperature T_{cold} and output temperature T_{warm} . T_{warm} corresponds to the temperature of the heating circuit in buildings or district heating networks, and T_{cold} to the temperature of the ambient heat source. Both temperatures vary throughout the year depending on the respective heat source (e.g. geothermal or solar thermal).

The maximum COP is described as:

$$COP_{max} = \frac{1}{\eta_c} = \frac{T_{warm}}{T_{warm} - T_{cold}}$$

The quality grade η_{HP} of a heat pump is expressed by the following statement:

$$\eta_{HP} = \frac{COP}{COP_{max}} = \frac{Q_c}{W * COP_{max}}$$

After reformulations, using the equation for COP_{max} and η_{HP} , the heat output Q_c can be stated as:

$$Q_C = \eta_{HP} * COP_{max} * W = \eta_{HP} * \frac{T_{warm}}{T_{warm} - T_{cold}} * W$$

or rearranged as the expression for the electricity input W :

$$W = \frac{1}{\eta_{HP} * \frac{T_{warm}}{T_{warm} - T_{cold}}} * Q_C$$

The time dependency of the efficiency is implemented in the model via using a new parameter called *TimeDepEfficiency*. Its value is specific to the region (r), technology (t), hour (l), and year (y).

The parameter is added to the equation *Eba4_RateOfFuelUse1* in GENeSYS-MOD v3.0:

$$\begin{aligned} &RateOfActivity(y, l, t, m, r) * InputActivityRatio(r, t, f, m, y) * TimeDepEfficiency(r, t, l, y) \\ &= RateOfUseByTechnologyByMode(y, l, t, m, f, r)^1 \end{aligned}$$

The $RateOfActivity(y, l, t, m, r)$ corresponds to Q_C and $RateOfUseByTechnologyByMode(y, l, t, m, f, r)$ to W . Hence, the reciprocal quality grade of heat pumps η_{HP} is implemented as the $InputActivityRatio(r, t, f, m, y)$. The $TimeDepEfficiency(r, t, l, y)$ for heat pumps is the reciprocal of the quotient $\frac{T_{warm}}{T_{warm} - T_{cold}}$. For all other technologies, the $TimeDepEfficiency(r, t, l, y)$ equals 1.

As a further new parameter in GENeSYS-MOD, the loss factor LF for district heating networks is implemented. The factor ensures that heat transfer losses are considered in the model. The factor is constant within a year and can vary from year to year and region to region. The factor is added in the equation *Eba11_EnergyBalanceEachTS5*:

$$\begin{aligned} &Production(y, l, f, r) \\ &= LF(y, f, r) * Demand(y, l, f, r) + Use(y, l, f, r) + NetTrade(y, l, f, r) \\ &+ Curtailment(y, l, f, r) \end{aligned}$$

B. Heating sector in Berlin

a. Heating demand in Berlin

In 2020, Berlins heating demand equaled 37 TWh (Dunkelberg et al. 2021, 52). Heat is demanded at different temperature levels. Usually, a distinction between residential heat (i.e. buildings) (consisting of space heating and hot water supply) and process heat is made (see Figure 1). Based on the application balances of AG Energiebilanzen, the energy sources are divided into different forms of heat.

¹ $y = year, l = timeslice\ or\ hour, t = technology, m = mode\ of\ operation, r = region.$

Total heat demand: 37TWh

Figure 1: Heating demand in Berlin in 2020.

Source: Own illustration based on Dunkelberg et al. (2021, 52).

In Berlin, heat demand for space heating dominates with a 76% share (ca. 28TWh), followed by hot water with 16% (ca. 6TWh). Process heat only plays a minor role since Berlin's industrial sector is limited.

b. Heating supply in Berlin

Heat supply is realized through decentral and central generation. In 2020, district heating accounted for approximately 32% (12 TWh) of total energy consumption for residential and process heat (see Figure 2 and Table 1). Nevertheless, the respective share of energy consumption through fossil gas usage in decentral heat supply dominates with over 43%. Since fossil gas is also used in district heating generation, overall fossil gas consumption for heat generation is even higher (see chapter c for district heating in Berlin). In third place, oil continues to be an essential energy source for Berlin's heat generation. The share of renewable energies (e.g. solar thermal, biomass, ambient heat) was hardly significant in 2020.

Table 1: Final energy consumption of Berlin heat supply in 2020 (in GWh).

2020	Residential heat	Process heat	Total	Share of total
District heating	11,016	848	11,864	32.3%
Oil	5,944	128	6,072	16.5%
Fossil gas	14,759	1,257	16,016	43.6%
Solar thermal	28	0	28	0.1%
Biomass	235	7	242	0.7%
Power	1,646	590	2,236	6.1%
Coal	59	23	82	0.2%
Ambient heat	162	1	163	0.4%
Total	33,849	2,854	36,703	100%

Source: Dunkelberg et al. (2021, 104f.).

Figure 2: Final energy consumption for residential and process heat in 2020 (in GWh).

By 2020, about 275,000 gas boilers and 56,000 oil boilers were providing residential heating (see Table 2). The current form of the §72 GEG (Building Energy Act) stipulates that radiators must be replaced after 30 years at the latest, which will require the replacement of 30,000 oil boilers and nearly 150,000 gas boilers until 2030 (Dunkelberg et al. 2021, 103).

Table 2: Installed heating technology in the residential sector.

Technology (pcs.)	2020
Gas boiler	275,060
Oil boiler	55,870
Heat pump	7,000
Biomass	1,070

Source: Based on Dunkelberg et al. (2021, 103).

c. District heating in Berlin

Following decentral fossil gas, district heating is the second most crucial energy supply in Berlin's heating market, with 11.8 TWh in 2020 (see Figure 3). Covering a total length of over 2200 km, the district heating network in Berlin is the largest in Europe after Moscow and Warsaw (BTB 2022; FHW 2022; Bloß 2020, 153; Ritzau, Langrock, and Michels 2019). Every year, it is extended by more than 20 km and connected to about 400 new buildings (Ritzau, Langrock, and Michels 2019, 6).² Berlin's district heating is not a single network but consists of 70 sub-networks. As the leading provider, Vattenfall supplies 90% of Berlin's district heating demand (Ritzau, Langrock, and Michels 2019, 5). The second-largest network is operated by the Neukölln district heating plant with a supply share of 2.3%, partly obtaining heat from Vattenfall's grid. The last operator highlighted is BTB, with several smaller networks producing a total of 600 GWh (5.1%) (BTB 2022).

² This corresponds to 25,000 new flat unit equivalents of 4,5kW each.

With a share of 55%, fossil gas also dominates centralized district heating. It is burned in Combined Heat and Power (CHP) plants and gas boilers to cover peak loads. Coal-fired CHP plants generate 16% of district heating in Berlin and will operate until 2030. Renewable energy and other energy sources each account for 14%. These primarily include waste incineration and biomass.

Figure 3: Fuel demand for district heating.

Source: Own illustration based on Amt für Statistik Berlin-Brandenburg (2021).

d. Emissions

In 2018, emissions from primary energy consumption amounted to 18.5 Mt CO₂, while final energy consumption led to emissions of 15.5 Mt CO₂. The development of emissions in Berlin since 1990 is depicted in Figure 4. CO₂ emissions have fallen by around 10 Mt (30%) in the last 30 years. The reduction is mainly caused by the replacement of outdated power plants and decentral heating technology.

Figure 4: CO₂ emissions by primary and final energy consumption.

Source: Own illustration based on Amt für Statistik Berlin und Brandenburg (2021).

In 2018, the energy and transport sector each accounted for one-third of CO₂ emissions in Berlin (see Table 3). Around 4 Mt CO₂ were attributable to the decentral heating of buildings and the commercial, trade, and service sector.

Table 3: CO₂ emission for energy, industry, transportation, households, and services.

	Total	Energy sector	Industry	Transportation	Households and commercial sector
1990	26,780	14,065	1,545	4,269	6,902
2018	15,527	5,914	271	5,194	4,148

Source: Amt für Statistik Berlin und Brandenburg (2021).

C. Result tables

Table 4: Decentral residential heat capacity in GW (2020-2050).

Technology	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Biomass	0.12	0.09	0.07				
Coal	0.03	0.02					
Direct electric	0.82	0.62	0.46	0.35	0.36	0.43	0.72
Geothermal			0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
HP aerial	0.07	0.78	0.87	0.95	1.06	1.08	1.82
HP ground	0.01	0.01	0.19	0.21	0.28	0.30	0.38
Solar thermal	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
Oil boiler	2.97	2.17	1.37	0.86	0.54	0.34	
Gas boiler	7.38	5.39	3.64	3.58	2.79	2.29	1.44
Total	11.41	9.08	6.60	5.96	5.04	4.45	4.37

Table 5: (Decentral) residential heat supply in PJ (2020-2050).

Technology	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
District heating	43.97	42.26	44.91	44.28	42.06	39.94	37.98
Direct electric	5.19	5.26	5.33	5.4	5.47	5.54	5.61
Gas boiler	46.02	30.68	10.38	20.75	12.01	6.15	0.5
Geothermal			0.14	0.3	0.3	0.31	0.31
HP aerial	2.07	*24.21	24.52	24.84	25.17	25.49	25.82
HP ground	0.29	0.3	4.9	4.96	5.03	5.09	5.16
Oil boiler	20.45	8.36	16.71	0.33	0.17	0.09	
Total	117.99	111.07	106.89	100.86	90.21	82.61	75.38

*2025 is a modelled year. The increase to 24PJ will not be realized in reality however, the results highlight the significance of heat pumps for the decarbonization of the heating sector and the high pace needed to deploy this technology.

Table 6: District heating capacity in GW in LowRes scenario (2020-2050).

Technology	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Storage	0.062	0.062	0.062	0.139	0.292	0.335	0.44
Direct electric	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.383	0.43	0.529	0.54
HP data center		0.005	0.01	0.02	0.045	0.05	0.05
HP geothermal (deep)		0.063	0.119	0.12	0.124	0.125	0.125
HP geothermal (surf.)		0.046	0.095	0.096	0.098	0.1	0.1
HP river		0.063	0.116	0.118	0.125	0.125	0.125
HP solar thermal		0.002	0.004	0.046	0.085	0.086	0.088
HP wastewater		0.025	0.046	0.049	0.05	0.05	0.05
Biomass			0.109	0.117	0.13	0.137	0.145
Biomass CHP	0.12	0.121	0.123	0.125	0.142	0.153	0.154
Waste heat		0.06	0.06	0.06	0.1	0.1	0.1
Gas boiler	2.163	2.342	2.907	2.796	2.545	2.108	2.066
Gas CHP	1.986	1.986	1.986	1.519	1.519	1.285	1.285
Oil boiler	0.143	0.143					
Oil CHP	0.33						
Coal CHP	0.635	0.635	0.032				
Waste CHP	0.099	0.099	0.099	0.099	0.099	0.099	0.099
Electrolysis		0	0.002	0.002	0.008	0.036	0.036
Total	5.658	5.772	5.89	5.689	5.792	5.318	5.403

Table 7: District heating supply in PJ in LowRes scenario (2020-2050).

Technology	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Storage	0.87	0.88	0.89	1.22	4	4.06	4.73
Electrolysis		0	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Direct electric	0.02	0.04	1.27	5.07	9.54	10.39	10.53
HP data center		0.15	0.31	0.62	1.35	1.48	1.5
HP geothermal (deep)		1.93	3.67	3.72	3.76	3.81	3.86
HP geothermal (surface)		1.43	2.93	2.97	3.01	3.05	3.09
HP river		1.58	2.93	2.97	3.01	3.04	3.08
HP solar thermal		0.03	0.07	0.72	1.34	1.35	1.37
HP wastewater		0.77	1.43	1.45	1.47	1.49	1.51
Biomass			3.38	3.62	3.81	4.01	4.06
Biomass CHP	2.59	2.63	2.66	2.7	2.73	2.77	2.8
Gas boiler	4.22	4.56	5.95	5.58	3.14	2.62	1.96
Gas CHP	28.25	25.61	19.96	15.58	8.87	5.83	4.09
Waste heat		1.08	1.08	1.08	1.8	1.8	1.78
Coal CHP	8.91	3.43	0.69				
Oil boiler	0.72	0.08					
Oil CHP	0						
Waste CHP	2.69	2.28	1.86	1.45	1.45	1.45	1.45
Total	48.27	46.48	49.09	48.76	49.29	47.16	45.82

Table 8: Process heat supply in LowRes scenario by fuel in PJ (2020-2050).

Technology	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Biomass	0.0	0.7	1.4	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.6
Coal	1.0	0.5	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Electricity	0.5	1.3	2.4	3.1	3.1	3.2	3.3
Gas	8.8	8.0	5.8	4.4	1.8	0.9	0.1
Hydrogen				0.7	2.0	3.5	4.1
Oil	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
Total	10.3	10.5	9.8	9.6	8.3	9.1	9.1

Table 9: CO₂ emissions in the LowRes scenario in Mt (2020-2050).

Technology	2015	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Buildings	4.3	4.6	2.6	2.0	1.3	0.7	0.4	0.0
Industry	0.9	0.7	0.6	0.4	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.0
Power and district heat	6.1	6.0	4.3	2.5	1.9	1.0	0.5	0.0
Transportation	4.6	4.5	4.0	3.2	2.1	1.1	0.5	0.0
Total	15.9	15.8	11.5	8.2	5.6	3.0	1.4	0.0

Table 10: Installed capacities in Berlin's district heating network in GW in MedRes scenario (2020-2050).

Technology	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Storage	0.06	0.06	0.37	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45
Direct electric	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.17
HP data center		0.01	0.02	0.04	0.09	0.10	0.10
HP geo (deep)		0.13	0.24	0.24	0.25	0.25	0.25
HP geo (surface)		0.10	0.18	0.19	0.20	0.20	0.20
HP river		0.12	0.23	0.23	0.24	0.25	0.25
HP solar thermal					0.08	0.11	0.11
HP wastewater		0.05	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
Biomass		0.04	0.07	0.07	0.11	0.25	0.31
Biomass CHP	0.12	0.12	0.14	0.14	0.15	0.24	0.34
Waste heat		0.06	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12
Gas boiler	2.15	2.16	2.37	2.51	2.26	1.79	1.75
Gas CHP	1.98	1.98	1.98	1.52	1.52	1.29	1.29
Oil boiler	0.14	0.14					
Oil CHP	0.33						
Coal CHP	0.64	0.64	0.03				
Waste CHP	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
Electrolysis		0.00	0.01	0.06	0.11	0.20	0.25
Total	5.65	5.82	6.09	5.89	5.90	5.57	5.79

Table 11: District heating production in Berlin MedRes (2020-2050).

in PJ	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Storage	0.85	0.86	4.13	4.81	5.91	5.99	6.07
Electrolysis	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.23	0.24	0.24	0.24
Direct electric	0.01	0.04	0.42	0.43	0.43	0.96	0.97
HP data center	0.00	0.30	0.60	1.19	2.67	2.93	2.97
HP geothermal (deep)	0.00	3.86	7.16	7.26	7.35	7.45	7.54
HP geothermal (surface)	0.00	2.94	5.58	5.68	5.79	5.87	5.94
HP river	0.00	3.01	5.72	5.79	5.90	6.01	6.09
HP solar thermal	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.18	1.67	1.70
HP wastewater	0.00	1.49	2.81	2.86	2.90	2.93	2.97
Biomass	0.00	1.20	2.25	2.28	2.31	2.43	2.46
Biomass CHP	2.60	2.63	3.02	3.06	3.19	3.24	3.28
Gas boiler	4.41	3.82	2.88	3.73	2.49	1.76	1.38
Gas CHP	28.22	19.42	13.09	11.43	7.25	4.01	2.52
Waste heat	0.00	1.08	2.16	2.14	2.16	2.16	2.16
Waste CHP	2.69	2.28	1.86	1.45	1.45	1.45	1.45
Coal CHP	8.88	3.43	0.69	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Oil boiler	0.71	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Oil CHP	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total	48.37	46.45	52.39	52.34	51.23	49.09	47.74

Table 12: Heat generation, installed capacities, and full load hours of district heating technologies in Berlin in 2045.

in 2045	PJ	GWh	GW	Full load hour
Electrolysis	0.3	84	0.204	412
Gas boiler	1.7	485	1.792	271
Gas CHP	4.0	1101	1.285	857
Direct electric	1.0	268	0.120	2230
Biomass	2.4	669	0.248	2701
Biomass CHP	3.2	899	0.243	3700
HP geothermal (surface)	5.9	1631	0.200	8155
HP geothermal (deep)	7.4	2066	0.250	8263
HP data center	2.9	815	0.100	8151
HP wastewater	2.9	815	0.100	8155
Waste heat	2.2	600	0.120	4997
Waste CHP	1.3	352	0.099	3554
HP river	6.0	1668	0.250	6672
HP solar thermal	1.7	467	0.112	4163
Total	42.9	11,921	5.123	-

Table 13: Process heat generation in Berlin by fuel in MedRes scenario (2020-2050).

in PJ	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Fossil/Synth. Gas	8.80	8.19	5.95	4.36	1.76	0.73	0.01
Biomass	0.03	0.85	1.52	2.08	2.10	2.19	2.26
Coal	0.96	0.44	0.21	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00
Electricity	0.49	1.06	2.23	3.11	3.16	3.24	3.34
Oil	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Hydrogen	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.33	2.78	3.47
Total	10.28	10.53	9.91	9.60	8.35	8.94	9.09

Table 14: CO₂ emissions in the MedRes scenario by sectors in Mt CO₂ (2020-2050).

Technology	2015	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Buildings	4.3	4.6	2.4	1.6	1.2	0.7	0.3	0.0
Industry	0.9	0.7	0.6	0.4	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.0
Power and district heat	6.1	6.0	3.6	1.6	1.5	1.0	0.5	0.0
Transportation	4.5	4.3	4.0	3.2	2.1	1.1	0.5	0.0
Total	15.8	15.7	10.6	6.8	5.1	2.9	1.4	0.0

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